

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Dynamic lactation responses to dietary crude protein oscillation in diets adequate and deficient in metabolizable protein in Holstein cows

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Supplementary Table 1. Dry matter intake regressed on experimental factors using a linear mixed model with fixed effects for cannulation status (S_j , where j = cannulated, non-cannulated), experimental period (E_k , where $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$), dietary CP level (P_l , where $l = LP, HP$), CP feeding pattern (F_m , where $m = OF, SF$), the interaction term between CP level and CP feeding pattern, and a fixed effect and all possible interactions between day (D_n , where $n = 25, 26, 27, 28$) with treatments. We included random intercepts for cow and cow:period and a random error term (ϵ_{ijklm} ; $n = 248$).

Fixed Effects	df	df	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
S	1	15.35	0.016	0.900
E	3	40.28	26.702	<0.001
D	3	174.00	2.434	0.067
P	1	40.06	0.284	0.597
F	1	40.74	0.676	0.416
D:P	3	174.00	3.076	0.029
D:F	3	174.00	1.194	0.314
P:F	1	40.05	0.355	0.555
D:P:F	3	174.00	1.969	0.120
Random Effects¹				
σ^2	2.98			
$\tau_{00 \text{ period:cow}}$	2.02			
$\tau_{00 \text{ cow}}$	4.67			
ICC	0.69			
N_{period}	4			
N_{cow}	17			
Observations	248			
Marginal R^2	0.298			
Conditional R^2	0.784			

¹The σ^2 , $\tau_{00 \text{ period:cow}}$ and $\tau_{00 \text{ cow}}$ represent the within-cow:period, between-cow:period, and between-cow variances, respectively. ICC shows the intraclass-correlation coefficient for the random effects.